

TABLE 1

Formula	Radius ratio	Phases present
1. $Y_2Ti_2O_7$	1.353 (1.672)	Pyrochlore $a=10.08 \text{ \AA}$
2. $(Y_{1-x}Ca_x)_2(Ti_{1-y}Nb_y)_2O_7$ x and $y=0.2$	1.370 (1.690)	Pyrochlore $a=10.12 \text{ \AA}$
3. $(Y_{1-x}Ca_x)_2(Ti_{1-y}Nb_y)_2O_7$ x and $y=0.3$	1.380 (1.694)	Pyrochlore $a=10.17 \text{ \AA}$ + Calcium niobate (Monoclinic) trace
4. $Ca_2Nb_2O_7$	1.435 (1.750)	Monoclinic ^{1,2}
5. $La_2Zr_2O_7$	1.443 (1.639)	Pyrochlore $a=10.80 \text{ \AA}$
6. $(La_{1-x}Ca_x)_2(Zr_{1-y}Nb_y)_2O_7$ x and $y=0.6$	1.438 (1.702)	Pyrochlore $a=10.59 \text{ \AA}$
7. $(La_{1-x}Ca_x)_2(Zr_{1-y}Nb_y)_2O_7$ x and $y=0.7$	1.437 (1.713)	Pyrochlore $a=10.57 \text{ \AA}$ + Cal. niobate (trace)
8. $(La_{1-x}Sr_x)_2(Zr_{1-y}Nb_y)_2O_7$ x and $y=0.3$	1.492 (1.726)	Pyrochlore $a=10.77 \text{ \AA}$
9. $(La_{1-x}Sr_x)_2(Zr_{1-y}Nb_y)_2O_7$ x and $y=0.4$	1.510 (1.756)	Pyrochlore $a=10.75 \text{ \AA}$ + $Sr_2Nb_2O_7$ (trace)
10. $Sr_2Nb_2O_7$	1.624 (1.953)	Monoclinic ^{1,2}

N. B. Radius ratios are calculated by using Ahrens radii for comparison with other workers while the values reported in parenthesis are obtained by using Shannon and Prewitt^{1,4} ionic radii.

1.61. In calculating radius ratio Ahrens ionic radii are used for comparison with other workers. Similarly Wilson¹¹ has also calculated limiting radius ratio for 3-4 (valence of cation at A site is three while that of at B site is four) as well as 2-5 pyrochlores. It is between 1.18 and 1.63.

Now if the radius ratios reported by Knop and Brisse⁶⁻⁷ and Wilson¹¹ are applied to the systems investigated in Table 1, then all the compositions except $Sr_2Nb_2O_7$ ($r_A/r_B=1.624$) should have shown pyrochlore structure. From the systems investigated by Brisse it can be concluded that radius ratio rule applies fairly well, if the substitution is carried out either at A or B site but when the substitutions are carried out at A as well as B sites and ions of different charges are used, the radius ratio criterion does not apply. In fact use of ions carrying different charges (in order to compensate valence changes) should have induced fields with lower symmetry causing distortion of the pyrochlore structure. But it is observed that the structure is not distorted but at certain critical concentration, which varies from system to system, formation of solid solution is prohibited forming two distinct crystallographic phases. Therefore, it can be concluded that when cations of different charges and radii are substituted at both the sites, radius ratio criterion seems to be relatively unimportant in determining the stability limit for pyrochlore structure.

References

1. D. D. HOGARTH, *Can. Min.*, 1959, **6**, 610.
2. F. JONA, G. SHIRANE and R. PRIPINSKY, *Phys. Rev.*, 1955, **98**, 903.
3. R. S. ROTH, *J. Res. Natl. Bur. Std.*, 1956, **56**, 17.
4. E. ALKESHIN and R. ROY, *J. Amer. Ceramic Soc.*, 1962, **45**, 18.
5. L. H. BRIXNER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 1065.
6. O. KNOP, F. BRISSE and L. CASTELLIZ, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 971.
7. F. BRISSE and O. KNOP, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1968, **46**, 859.
8. A. W. SLEIGHT, *Mat. Res. Bull.*, 1968, **3**, 699.
9. V. S. DARSHANE and V. V. DESHPANDE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 761.
10. V. S. DARSHANE and V. V. DESHPANDE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 229.
11. L. F. WILSON, Ph.D. Thesis, London University, 1958.
12. J. F. ROWLAND, N. F. H. BRIGHT and A. JONGEJAN, *Proc. 7th Ann. Conf. Ind. Appl. X-ray Analysis, Denver*, 1958.
13. K. SCHEUNEMANN and H. K. MULLER, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1679.
14. R. D. SHANNON and C. T. PREWITT, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1970, **B26**, 1076.

3-Aldehydosalicyledene Cyanoacetyl Hydrazone as a New Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Ferric Ions*

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Manuscript received 21 August 1979, accepted 30 November 1979

WHILE a number of compounds have been investigated as a reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of ferric ions. 3-Aldehydosalicyledene cyanoacetyl hydrazone (3-ASCAH) has not been investigated so far for this purpose. Fe^{3+} -3-ASCAH system was found to give stable reddish brown colour in acidic medium. The present article reports the use of 3-ASCAH as a new sensitive analytical reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of ferric ions at 370 nm in a pH range 4 to 5 and 50% ethanol-aqueous medium.

Experimental

Materials: All reagent and chemicals used in the present work were of Analar B.D.H. grade. Pure distilled water redistilled over alkaline permanganate and free from carbon dioxide, was used throughout the investigation.

Synthesis of Ligand: The 3-aldehydosalicylic acid and cyanoacetic acid hydrazide were prepared^{1,2} and taken in equimolecular proportions in

* Presented at Indian Science Congress, 1979 (Part III-2, p. 1 in Abstract).

alcoholic medium. After refluxion for two hours, 3-aldehydosalicyledene cyanoacetyl hydrazone (3-ASCAH) separated as a crystalline compound. The deep yellow coloured needles of this Schiff base were purified by repeated crystallisation from alcohol. The compound is soluble in alcohol and dioxane with sharp m.p. 208°.

Apparatus : The absorbance measurements were done on Beckman DU spectrophotometer Model 109200 using a matched pair of 1 cm cuvettes. The Metrohm pH meter Model E-350A with wide range glass calomal electrode was used. Buffer solutions prepared of potassium hydrogen phthalate and borax were used for standardisation of the pH meter.

Stock Solutions :

Stock solution of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ of 3-aldehydosalicyledene cyanoacetyl hydrazone prepared by dissolving the requisite amount in ethanol. Standard solution of Fe(III) of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ was prepared in double distilled water and estimated by EDTA³.

Sequence of Addition of Reagents : No change in the absorbance or colour intensity of the complex was observed if the order of addition of reactants was changed.

Absorbance Spectrum : A solution of 1 ml of Iron stock solution and 1 ml of 3-ASCAH was adjusted to pH 5 while diluting with water to exactly 10 ml maintaining the 50% aqueous-ethanol (v/v) medium. An appropriate blank was prepared in a similar manner except that water was added in place of Iron solution. Absorbance measurements were made in the region 350-600 nm after the adjustment of pH. The reagent showed a sharp absorbance band due to Iron³⁺-3-ASCAH complex at 370 nm with the molar absorptivity of 1.292×10^5 litres/mole cm.

Effect of pH : The absorption characteristics of the complex in the pH range 4-5 showed a maximum colour with 3-ASCAH. The pH was adjusted with buffer.

Conformity to Beer's Law :

A number of solutions containing varying amount of Iron and 0.2 ml of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ 3-ASCAH solution at pH 5 ± 0.1 were prepared and tested for the confirmation of the colour system for Beer's Law, which was seen to be followed at 370 nm over the concentration range 6 to 70 ppm of Iron for 1.0 cm cells; the absorbance readings were low below 6 ppm of Iron.

Sensitivity and Molar Absorptivity of the Complex : The spectrophotometric sensitivity of the colour

reaction in terms of Sandell's definition⁴ is $0.043 \mu g$ of Iron per cm^2 for $\log I_0/I = 0.001$. The molar absorptivity calculated from a plot of Beer's Law is 1.292×10^5 litres/mol. cm. at 370 nm.

Effect of Diverse ions and Media : The effect of different inorganic and organic species was studied for solutions containing 10 ppm of Iron and 0.2 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$) of the reagent and the varying concentrations of each ion were tested in a total volume of 10 ml at pH 5. The absorbance measurements showed that Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Hg^{2+} interfere in this colour reaction even in small quantities. The presence of acetate ion in more than 0.01 M increases the error by 1.5%.

The alcohol contents must not be less than 35% (v/v), otherwise the reagent is precipitated.

Conclusion : 3-ASCAH may prove to be a versetile reagent for the determination and estimation of Iron spectrophotometrically in presence of several anions and cations.

References

1. J. DUFF and E. BILLS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1987.
2. D. CHAKRAVARTY, A. BOSE and S. BOSE, *Pharm. Sci.*, 1964, **53**, 1036-39.
3. F. J. WELCHER, *The Analytical uses of EDTA*. Von Nostrand, Princeton, 1951.
4. E. B SANDELL, *Colorimetric Determination of Trace of Metals*, Interscience Publishers, INC, New York, 1965.

A Novel Spray Reagent for Plant Pigments

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Manuscript received 7 September 1979, accepted 30 November 1979

THE present investigation was carried out with a view to find some new spray reagents for detecting the presence of hydroxyl groups adjacent to carbonyl groups in the quinones and flavones. This was achieved by paper chromatographic procedures involving the use of *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water $\left(4 : 1 : 5 \frac{v}{v}\right)$ as solvent and 1% aqueous sodium vanadate as spray reagent when the plant pigments were present in amounts of at least $5 \mu g$ each.

This reagent has shown better results on comparing with the following popular spray reagents¹⁻⁴ viz. ammonia vapours, *p*-toluene sulphonic acid, iodine vapours, methanolic aluminium chloride, methanolic sulphuric acid, 1%